

SUSTAINING ECONOMIES AND ENHANCING DYNAMIC STRUCTURES

Deliverable 9.1
Communication plan

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
B/W	Black and White
C&D	Communication and dissemination
CMYK	Cyan, Magenta, Yellow, and Key
Cop	Community of practice
DoA	Description of Action
EIP-Agri	European Innovation Partnerships for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
EU	European Union
HEX	Hexadecimal colour system
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MENA	Middle East North Africa
N.A.	Not Available
PDF	Portable Document Format
RGB	Red, Green, and Blue
TV	Television
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

History of changes

Version	Author	Date	Comments
0.1	ENCO	11/04/2024	Preliminary ToC
0.2	ENCO	13/05/2024	First version
0.3	INRAT	27/05/2024	First revision
1.0	ENCO	30/05/2024	Final version

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Executive Summary

Effective communication is a cornerstone of a successful project management process. Sharing constantly information about the activities and the achievements of the results of a project is essential to reach the target groups and an increasingly wider audience.

The following Communication Plan is a deliverable of the Work Package 9, specifically of the activity 9.1 - Communication Plan. This document outlines the strategy that will be implemented to ensure a correct and continuous communication, dissemination, and exploitation of the results for the whole duration of the project.

Target audiences, key messages and communication channels selected will be listed in this document. The following communication strategy will examine the results obtained through the means identified at the beginning of the project and being a living document, if necessary, it will be modified during the project duration in order to achieve maximum impact.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Background

In MENA region countries cereals represent an essential component in people's diets: being very rich in nutritional properties, they register the highest consumption average in the world with a rate of 200 kg per person per year.

In recent years, due to a strong global population growth, demand has increased but, due to catastrophic climate events and problematic geopolitical factors, the supply chain has been severely damaged. The price for grains has increased making it difficult, for many customers, to purchase a nutrient necessary to a healthy and well-balanced diet. Moreover, the rhythms of people's lives are becoming day by day more frenetic so that consumers often prefer functional processed foods which can be harmful to health.

Being the MENA region the secondary diversity centre of cereals, SEEDS project aims to revitalize the cultivation of ancient grains in the area because their strong resilience to current climate conditions, pests and diseases can be the right ally to produce a real change in the agricultural system.

SEEDS project will implement innovative solutions for achieving its objectives by developing a new innovative and sustainable farming system through new agri-food business models (AKIS), LLs and an inclusive digital platform to spread knowledge and information about the topics of the project.

1.2. Objectives of the SEEDS Communication Plan

The objective of this Communication Plan is to share information and spread knowledge in a clear and transparent manner in order to reach and actively involve the target groups identified and promote the cooperation among all partners.

More specifically, the SEEDS communication strategy aims to:

- Raise consumers, retailers, and policymakers’ awareness about the nutritional and agronomic value of ancient grains encouraging them to adopt a healthy lifestyle;
- ensure the long-term maintenance of the project result guaranteeing their replicability;
- promote community empowerment and encouraging policies that support gender-inclusive agricultural practices, highlighting the pivotal role women play in sustainable rural development.

1.3. Evaluation of effectiveness of the Communication Plan

For the whole duration of the project the communication strategy will be monitored, and the effectiveness of the proposed activities will be evaluated. Where needed, corrective actions will be applied in order to lead to the achievement of the objectives set out.

Systematic analyses of engagement data will be conducted for the C&D tools established. Will be monitored parameters like: No. of followers on social media pages, No. of interactions to the posts, No. of users registered on the Knowledge sharing platform, No. of visits to the website, No. of women and young people participating to the events, No. of downloads of documents for public use available on the platform (English and Arabic) etc.

These data will allow us to identify strengths and weaknesses and boost or improve a tool when needed. Below it is possible to consult the Evaluation of effectiveness table, that together with the C&D Logbook (see Section 3.2) will be used to keep track of all C&D activities and aggregated numbers for KPIs.

C&D TOOLS	KPI IDENTIFIED	KPI	MONTH	RESULTS ACHIEVED (M3)
Website	N. of visits	3000	M36	N.A.
Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter YouTube)	N. of followers	2500	M36	200 (177+23)
	N. of posts	1500	M36	16 (8+8)
	N. of views on the posts	3500	M36	587

Promotional materials	N. of downloads of materials	5000	M36	N.A.
Project videos	Presentation video	1	M6	N.A.
	Final video	1	M36	N.A.
Cross-fertilisation events	N. of attendees in cross-fertilisation events	250	M36	N.A.
Organization of event for the empowerment of women and young people in agriculture	N. of events organized	5	M36	N.A.
Participation in relevant events	N. of participations in PR dissemination events	30	M36	N.A.
	N. of participations in women and young people empowerment events	350	M36	N.A.
Scientific publications	N. of publications in international peer reviewed journals	10	M36	N.A.
	N. of publications in magazines, specialized websites, International Conference Act	20		N.A.

EIP Multiactor Practice Abstracts	N. of EIP Multiactor Practice Abstracts	More than 12	M36	N.A.
Poster presentations	N. of poster presentations	4	M36	N.A.

Table 1: Evaluation of effectiveness

2. Communication strategy

Communication is essential to guarantee the success of a project not just because it allows to share information to stakeholders about objectives, activities, and results but also because it is the mean through which cooperation among partners is fostered. Indeed, an effective communication strategy is capable to create alliances and to ensure the long-term maintenance of project outcomes and impact.

It is very important to know the audience the project will be referring to: it is essential to understand how they communicate and identify the most effective methods to attract their interest.

In the following paragraphs implementation strategy, target audience, project identity and communication tools that will be used by all partners to reach the public will be identified.

2.1. Implementation strategy

Drawing up a communication plan is essential to define its objectives and the tactics to use to achieve them and to identify the key messages the project wants to convey. To successfully execute the communication strategy, SEEDS will follow an implementation plan that will include the phases described below.

- Planning;
- Performing;
- Reporting phases.

This cycle is connected to each communication activity of the project, guaranteeing constant and effective reporting of all project results to the target audience according to the project needs.

2.2. Target audience & Key Messages

Identifying the target groups of a project is fundamental to achieve success: knowing the audience allows to adapt the strategy and the messages to their necessities and interests, improving the effectiveness of the whole project.

Each target group has unique and distinct interests that drive their preferences and decisions. This diversity of interests requires a targeted and personalized approach so that the key messages of the

SEEDS project depend on the type of audience which they are addressed to. In the following table, the main messages to be transmitted for each type of audience are indicated.

TARGET GROUP	KEY MESSAGES
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By implementing the SEEDS new agricultural system environmental impact will be reduced and biodiversity will be preserved; • The economic development of MENA countries and their land productivity will be boosted; • Cereal supply chain resilience will be improved, driving long-term impactful outcomes. • The valorized ancient grain will not compete with the improved varieties
Agri-food industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEEDS will enhance agri-food industries' capabilities in adopting ancient grains and adapting them to meet industrial requirements, fostering a more resilient cereal sector and unlock new business opportunities.
Farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEEDS will encourage them to produce adapted crops, suitable for sustainable agricultural managements and practices and capable of producing healthy, nutritious, and safe raw materials; • New business models, including short sustainable, certified value chains, will be proposed to ensure faire revenues for all.
Food services and retailers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEEDS will help food service companies and retailers to adopt new habits for enhancing consumers' adherence to new foods based on ancient grains.
Consumers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEEDS will create 8 new products to deliver concrete and healthy choices for consumers; • SEEDS will reduce the cereal demand by considering reaching fair prices for the new products, supported by social policies when relevant.
Research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEEDS will collect and produce extensive data on cereal supply chains, policies, and food choices; • SEEDS will support ongoing initiatives and enable future multidisciplinary research for a resilient cereal sector.
Press and Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By sharing practical guidelines, SEEDS will support press and media in delivering right messages towards large audience for promoting the consumption of ancient grains and their roles.
Other PRIMA projects, Horizon Europe projects, EU initiatives and international networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEEDS will create synergies with several Horizon Europe, PRIMA, INTERREG and LIFE projects and with EU and international initiatives, focusing on synergies that exist between projects and how mutual benefits can emerge through collaboration.

Table 2: Target groups & Key Messages

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2.3. Project Identity

Project identity encompasses all the elements that make SEEDS distinguishable and recognizable: the elements that are listed in the following paragraphs define project’s essence and values, and public perception depends on it.

2.3.1. Project Logo

ENCO, as responsible of materials design, has developed a visual identity for SEEDS project, to support the partners to communicate more effectively with all target groups.

For this purpose, an appropriate visual identity for the project has been developed.

The idea is to make every project’s document, actuation, or communication completely identifiable having bigger impact and making trackable the storytelling and the evolution of the project.

VERSION	LOGO
Positive version	
B/W version	

Negative version

Table 3: Logo Versions

The logo cannot be used with different colours from the ones stated in this manual, proportions will never be altered and any use on coloured background should never alter its visibility.

2.3.2. Graphical Layout Guidelines

The Visual Identity Manual gives SEEDS a recognisable image. The style, the formal coherence and the consistency in a project's communication defines its personality and gives the possibility to be reminded by a large audience.

Corporate Typography:

The font family chosen is Calibri.

CMYK: 0%, 10%, 55%, 8%**RGB:** 235, 212, 105**HEX:** #EBD469

2.3.3. Template Toolkit

In order to ensure effective and coherent communication, it is essential to have well-structured template toolkits. These tools provide a basis for the creation of SEEDS' documents and presentations, improving the project visual identity and its perception of to the public.

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Two of them are presented in this paragraph, one must be used for the deliverables and the other for the PowerPoint presentations. No one, other than the members of the consortium, is authorized to use the following templates for other purposes that do not include the SEEDS project. All consortium members must use them in any deliverable or presentation performed.

**SUSTAINING ECONOMIES AND
ENHANCING DYNAMIC
STRUCTURES**

**DELIVERABLE X.X
WPX**

Figure 1: SEEDS Deliverable Template

SUSTAINING ECONOMIES AND ENHANCING DYNAMIC STRUCTURES

Presentation title

Meeting name
Venue, date (XX Month XXXX)

Figure 2: SEEDS Presentation Template

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2.4. Communication Tools

In a world which is increasingly interconnected, information has become much more accessible. Today there are many means that offer unique and effective advantages and by which people can communicate and stay up to date. The following paragraph lists the tools through which contents concerning SEEDS project will be communicated and disseminated.

2.4.1. SEEDS website

SEEDS website will be available from M3 by following the URL: (www.seeds-prima.eu), and it will be the main source of information about the project’s objectives, progress, and results. It will be constantly updated with new contents as the project progresses, in order to maintain stakeholders involved in the long term.

SEEDS website will be well-structured and easily accessible, even for an audience that is not familiar with technology. Contents will be available in English and Arabic language offering an appealing user experience to target users and stakeholders will be able to contact the team. It will provide the section explained in the following table:

SECTION	FUNCTION
About us	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What we do: this section will provide general information about the project, its origin and values, the consortium, their mission their approach and their actions. • Project team: photos and short presentation of the team and their role within the project. • Consortium: An area dedicated to a short presentation of the partnership. Each partner will be represented by the company’s logo provided with a hyperlink to the company’s website. • External Advisory Board: an area where external experts will provide advice about strategies and management of the project.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In this section SEEDS’ objectives will be listed in a clear and transparent way to make them understandable to a wide range of people.
Workplan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phases: this area will be dedicated to demonstrating the various steps of the implementation process of the project. • Work packages: this section will show all the activities that will be implemented during the project by each partner.
News and events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A section where all updates regarding the project, such as conferences, events or other news will be published.
Platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A knowledge sharing platform free accessible to stakeholders along MENA & EU supply chain to provide an overall vision of SEEDS’s main outcomes

Download	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The section where all downloading material will be shared (flyers, brochures or other documents).
Private area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A section which redirects partners to the private SharePoint working space.
Stay connected with SEEDS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A section where the user can easily reach the SEEDS social media pages and get in touch with the Project Coordinator and the Scientific and Technical Coordinator.

Table 4: SEEDS website structure

Below it is possible to see a screenshot of the SEEDS website homepage.

Figure 3: SEEDS Website Homepage

With the aim of expanding the audience, a **calendar** has been created by ENCO and shared with all the other partners in the TEAMS shared folder in order to monitor the publication of at least one news item on SEEDS website every month.

	MONTHS	DEADLINE	PARTNER	SENT TO ENCO (yes/no)	PUBLISHED ON THE WEBSITE (yes/no)
M3	MAY 2024	20 MAY 2024	ENCO		
M4	JUNE 2024	20 JUNE 2024	UNINA		
M5	JULY 2024	20 JULY 2024	FFI		
M6	AUGUST 2024	20 AUGUST 2024	ARC		

M7	SEPTEMBER 2024	20 SEPTEMBER 2024	CEEBA		
M8	OCTOBER 2024	20 OCTOBER 2024	HEALTHTECH		
M9	NOVEMBER 2024	20 NOVEMBER 2024	CNTA		
M10	DECEMBER 2024	20 DECEMBER 2024	ITENE		
M11	JANUARY 2025	20 JANUARY 2025	CERTH		
M12	FEBRUARY 2025	20 FEBRUARY 2025	NARC		
M13	MARCH 2025	20 MARCH 2025	GIDC		
M14	APRIL 2025	20 APRIL 2025	IAV		
M15	MAY 2025	20 MAY 2025	CAIAC		
M16	JUNE 2025	20 JUNE 2025	INRAT		
M17	JULY 2025	20 JULY 2025	INGC		
M18	AUGUST 2025	20 AUGUST 2025	CMA		

Table 5: Calendar of News Items

2.4.2. Social Media

Social media have become crucial tools for promotional purposes. Through these platforms, it is possible to engage a wider audience in a simpler and faster way. The use of a clear and transparent language is very important to reach everyone. Furthermore, the shareable nature of the published contents allows an effective dissemination of them, thus increasing the visibility of the project.

Currently, SEEDS project has three important social media profile:

LinkedIn: @SEEDS Project (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/seeds-eu-project/?viewAsMember=true>)

Figure 4: SEEDS LinkedIn Page

Twitter: @SeedsEu (<https://twitter.com/SeedsEu>)

Figure 5: SEEDS Twitter Page

YouTube: @SEEDS-mt3ky (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZgUzDhqDep8scSxUhuFQuA>)

Figure 6: SEEDS YouTube channel

The objective is that of raise awareness in the public about SEEDS initiatives, results, and action.

Social media contents will be generated by ENCO, and it is required the collaboration of all partners: the expected contribution involves becoming followers of SEEDS social media platforms and sharing the contents among their companies and personal’s networks.

By encompassing a multiple range of countries, SEEDS project can cause an exponential ripple effect at global level if the cooperation among all partners is active and constant.

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2.4.3. E-newsletter

A periodic e-Newsletter will be issued every six months. This constitutes one of the principal communication tools to connect with interested stakeholders. The first newsletter and the newsletter template are in preparation, and they will be ready at the end of August. The newsletter will be developed in English, available both in HTML and PDF format and uploaded to the “Downloads” section of the project website. The newsletters will be sent via the partners’ networks and contact databases. The website of the project will feature an option to allow interested parties to enrol for the newsletter. Each issue will be announced ahead of time through the project communication channels, including other relevant newsletters and websites with the aim of maximise the outreach. Each newsletter will include an overview of the last progress achieved, an outlook for the next period of project activities and other relevant news concerning the project and surrounding environment.

2.4.4. Scientific publications

Scientific publications are a very important component for a research and innovation project like SEEDS. Being subject to rigorous reviews by experts on the field before being accepted for the publication, they represent a tool that gives reliability to the information contained.

One of the target audiences consists of experts and the scientific community who will be able to use the new discovers to continue the research from an advanced point. This aspect is relevant because by fostering cooperation and the exchange of ideas the impact of the project could reach a global scale. This will be possible through emphasizing on the choice of international journals, particularly those with open access highly cited and through organizing and participating to periodic science outreach events to promote the results.

Through popularizing the content of the articles, extension supports and social networks, and media SEEDS can target also Technical and famers communities who will adopt newly developed technologies and contribute to their dissemination.

SEEDS will publish at least 10 publications in international peer reviewed journals, 20 publications in magazines, specialized websites, International Conference Act, 13 and EIP Multiactor Practice Abstracts in EIP-Agri website, and 4 poster presentations. These publications will summarize technical social and policy research findings, supporting the uptake of SEEDS data and results for further research and practical solutions.

Beside publications, SEEDS will enhance the visibility of the final project event before and after its occurrence through utilizing online and offline marketing, engaging with social media, collecting feedback, utilizing media coverage.

2.4.5. Press Media Campaign

A strong presence in media is crucial to enhance SEEDS’ visibility and public awareness about the topic of the project. SEEDS press media campaign will increase diffusion and credibility of the project.

Still are a lot the people who read printed publications, watch TV, and listen to the radio, and daily press and media communication plays an important role in the public perceptions. By sharing practical guidelines, SEEDS will support press and media in delivering right messages towards large audience for promoting the consumption of ancient grains and their roles.

Each partner for the respective country will propose a list of potential TVs, radio, and newspaper here to spread SEEDS news and contents.

2.4.6. Video Clips

ENCO is responsible for the creation of two short videos throughout the lifetime of the project.

The first one will present SEEDS' objectives; the creation of this video aims to capture the viewer's attention in a more engaging and dynamic way because of the extremely effectiveness of communicating of the multimedia experience. The main objective of this short video is to raise awareness on SEEDS topics and to make more understandable the global situation about the cereal value and supply chain. This will be ready by month 6.

The other one will be created at the end of the project, and it will show its results and impact. A results collection video represents a powerful mean for showing the success of the project and all achievements obtained. Moreover, being a visual-attractive content, it can be shared and disseminated on the social platforms, broadening the impact and inspiring other people to continue SEEDS actions.

2.4.7. Digital and Printed Material

ENCO, as WP9 leader, is responsible for the digital and printed promotional materials for SEEDS project.

The objective of the material is to raise awareness about the project's topic and results. The printed material consists of project flyers, posters, and gadgets that will be distributed at any events attended to support SEEDS communication and branding actions.

With the aim to make any event more sustainable and in order to increasingly promote green actions, paper waste will be limited to the essential: the printing of what can be viewed and downloaded online will be reduced in the whole respect of the environment.

Digital materials are available on all social media platforms and will be uploaded on the promotional materials section of the project website. It will be available in English and Arabic, not excluding that all partners may translate it in the language of their county, if needed.

Figure 7: SEEDS Roll-up

Follow us

- [seeds-eu-project](#)
- [@SeedsEu](#)
- [@SEEDS-mt3ky](#)
- [www.seeds-prima.eu](#)

enco

enco
EUROPEAN NETWORK OF CEREAL ORGANISATIONS

AGRIARIA
AGRICULTURE IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AREA

ARC
AGRICULTURE RESEARCH CENTRE

CeTA
CEREAL TECHNOLOGY AND APPLICATIONS

NARC
NORTH AFRICAN RESEARCH CENTRE

FUTURE FOOD INSTITUTE

ITENE
INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGICAL NETWORK FOR EUROPEAN NUTRITION

CERTH
CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY

CMA
CEREAL MANUFACTURING ASSOCIATION

HEALTHTECH

INGC
INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

CAIAC
CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURAL INNOVATION AND ADAPTATION

CNTA
CENTRO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

SUSTAINING ECONOMIES AND ENHANCING DYNAMIC STRUCTURES

PRIMA
IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AREA

Type of action: Research and Innovation
Total budget: € 2.748.875,00
Starting date: 01/03/2024
Duration: 36 months

Project Coordinator - ENCO SRL
 Scientific & Technical Coordinator - INRAT

This project is part of the PRIMA Programme supported by the European Union" under the Grant Agreement number 2332 Call 2023 Section 1 AGROFOOD RIA

Figure 8: SEEDS Brochure external pages

Cereal grains have been the cornerstone of human diet for thousands of years and have greatly influenced human civilization.

To address the current lack within Mediterranean countries due to climate changes, **SEEDS** aims to revive the cultivation of ancient grains in **4 MENA countries** in order to foster local supply and value chains.

Jordan

Morocco

Egypt

Tunisia

Through the creation of a **digital platform**, we aim to improve access to information and facilitate the sharing of knowledge to a wider public: **greater awareness** will create more opportunities in agriculture and will guide consumer choice towards healthier food..

Have you ever desired healthy functional foods?

In response to your preferences for functional foods, SEEDS will foster food environments by introducing **eight** innovative products made from ancient grains.

SCAN ME

Visit the **website** and **SEEDS social channels** to learn more and join us in furthering our mission!

PHASE 1 Analysis of the current cereal sector status

PHASE 2 Exploratory research

PHASE 3 Co-creation for impactful solutions, validation via LLS, CWGs and CoP

PHASE 4 ICT tools development

PHASE 5 Sustained impact and post-project exploitation roadmaps

Figure 9: SEEDS Brochure internal pages

2.4.8. Participation to related events and conferences

Participation to events and conferences regarding the issues addressed by SEEDS is crucial to enrich the awareness of all partners about the project relevance. These events offer the opportunity to connect with industry experts and allow participants to maintain a proactive approach to the environmental challenges we face and to become active actors and bearer of change. Choosing the right event for the project can have a significant impact on the success.

The idea is to start from M3 and take part at the events quarterly and the partners should attend at least 2 events for each of them.

An initial list of potentially interesting events is available below:

EVENT	DATE	PLACE
International Conference on Sustainable Development	11 - 12 September 2024	Rome, Italy
Precision Agriculture Conference	16 - 18 September 2024	Rome, Italy
AGBIOL 2024	18 - 20 September 2024	Edirne, Turkey
World Agri-Tech innovation summit	30 September-1 October 2024	London, UK
Euroseeds	13 - 16 October 2024	Copenhagen, Denmark
Effost	12 - 14 November 2024	Bruges, Belgium
International Quinoa Symposium	24 - 26 July 2024	Hohenheim, Germany
8th International Seed Congress	09-12 December 2024	Antalya, Türkiye
ISF World Seed Congress	TBD, 2025	TBD

Table 6: SEEDS potential events participation

2.4.9. SEEDS Final Event

ENCO is responsible for the organization of SEEDS final event: it is the culminant point that allows all partners to showcase and celebrate the successes of the project involving as many stakeholders as possible, share knowledge and plan future actions to ensure the sustainability of results achieved in the long term.

It includes targeted transmission of articles in relevant trade and organization of workshops. In addition, to provided added value to the SEEDS end-users, EIP Multiactor Practice Abstracts will be prepared (in Italian, Spanish, French and Arab more than English - 1.000 to 1.500 characters) highlighting main practical recommendation (how can practitioner make use of SEEDS results).

Synergies and cross fertilization with other projects and initiatives will be pursued to capitalize on the mutual work and create value clusters, avoiding multiplication of efforts and optimizing access to results by industry and society.

3. Planning, Monitoring and Evaluation

A continuous tracking and monitoring of KPIs will be done considering the Evaluation of effectiveness strategy explained in the section 1.3. and using the internal monitoring tools developed by ENCO which can be consulted below.

3.1. Tools for Communication, Monitoring and Reporting

The monitoring and reporting phase are essential to ensure high quality and success of all the activities of the project. During the implementation of C&D actions of SEEDS project, data will be collected in the **Communication and Dissemination LogBook**.

All Communication and Dissemination activities must be recorded in this spreadsheet. All partners are responsible for properly filling this document. The list of activities that must be kept track within this tool are the ones below:

- Organization of Conferences
- Organization of Workshops
- Press releases
- Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publications
- Exhibitions
- Flyers
- Training
- Social media
- Twitter
- LinkedIn
- Website
- Participation to Conferences
- Participation to Workshops
- Participation to Events (other than Conferences or Workshops)
- Video/Films
- Brokerage Events
- Trade Fairs
- Participation in activities organized jointly with other EU projects
- Regarding participation in events, all partners will have to specify the categories and the number of stakeholders present (Scientific community, industry, civil society, general public, policy makers, media, investors, customers, other).

